

Nitrogen, a gasocrine signal, is sensed via gas-sensing gasoreceptor proteins such as *Escherichia coli* FNR protein

Savani Anbalagan^{1,2}

¹Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland.

²Correspondence

E-mail: savani.anbalagan@amu.edu.pl

Tel: +48 61 829 5905

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Understanding how organisms communicate is a fundamental question in biology and marks an evolutionarily important milestone. Organisms largely communicate via gas-based gasocrine, light-based photocrine, sound-based sonocrine, mineral/metal-based metallochrine, water-based aquacrine, and thermal radiation-based thermocrine signaling.¹ Due to the importance of gasocrine signaling for biotic life, how organisms can sense gasocrine signals such as O₂ (oxygen) via O₂-sensing protein gasoreceptors (or sensors) has been largely investigated in microorganisms.^{2,3} Even though nitrogen (N₂) is also one of the gasocrine signals, to the best of my knowledge and few other leading experts on nitrogen fixation and nitric oxide-dependent signaling, how organisms sense nitrogen *per se* is still unknown. I recently proposed that N₂ is likely sensed indirectly via ammonia-sensing proteins (gasoreceptors).⁴ But there must be other proteins that can sense N₂ *per se*. Just as the FeMo (iron-molybdenum) cofactor in nitrogenase can directly bind N₂, other FeMo-binding proteins with signaling domains may function as N₂-sensing proteins. Additionally, N₂ can also bind to Fe-S (nonheme iron-sulfur) clusters.⁵ But then if N₂ can bind to Fe-S clusters, this raises an important question on the interpretation of all the Fe-S-protein related experiments that were performed under N₂-rich anaerobic conditions in which N₂ was not considered as the ligand but merely as an anaerobic environment-inducing agent. For instance, the *Escherichia coli* Fe-S cluster-based dimeric transcription factor FNR (fumarate and nitrate reductase) can bind to specific DNA regions (FNR consensus motifs) under N₂-rich anaerobic condition but loses its dimerization state and DNA-binding ability under O₂-rich condition.⁶⁻⁸ But FNR is only addressed as an 'oxygen-sensing protein or oxygen sensor' or as 'global anaerobic transcription factor' and not as a N₂-sensing protein. If the anaerobic-specific DNA-binding transcriptional activity via FNR dimerization state is due to either N₂-interaction with FNR-bound Fe-S cluster or non-Fe-S salt bridge⁹, FNR is merely an N₂ gas (solute)-sensing gasoreceptor protein. Orthologues of FNR or other N₂-binding proteins with additional signaling domains are very likely putative N₂-sensing gasoreceptor proteins. Systemically identifying N₂- or other gas-sensing gasoreceptor proteins will help us understand gasocrine signaling and its role in civilizational diseases, antibiotic resistance, agricultural yields, causes for climate change and global warming.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

DISCLOSURE

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REFERENCES

1. Anbalagan S. Why do the majority of drugs fail in clinical trials? My search for a moksha in biology [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 May 14]; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/11079992>
2. Anbalagan S. Heme-based oxygen gasoreceptors. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab* 2024; 326:E178-81.
3. Anbalagan S. Oxygen is an essential gasotransmitter directly sensed via protein gasoreceptors. *Animal Models and Experimental Medicine* 2024; 7:189-93.
4. Anbalagan S. Nitrogen, a gasocrine signal, is likely sensed via ammonia-sensing gasoreceptors [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 May 14]; Available from: <https://zenodo.org/records/11180835>
5. Zambrano IC, Kowal AT, Mortenson LE, Adams MW, Johnson MK. Magnetic circular dichroism and electron paramagnetic resonance studies of hydrogenases I and II from *Clostridium pasteurianum*. *J Biol Chem* 1989; 264:20974-83.
6. Lazazzera BA, Bates DM, Kiley PJ. The activity of the *Escherichia coli* transcription factor FNR is regulated by a change in oligomeric state. *Genes Dev* 1993; 7:1993-2005.
7. Lazazzera BA, Beinert H, Khoroshilova N, Kennedy MC, Kiley PJ. DNA binding and dimerization of the Fe-S-containing FNR protein from *Escherichia coli* are regulated by oxygen. *J Biol Chem* 1996; 271:2762-8.
8. Khoroshilova N, Popescu C, Münck E, Beinert H, Kiley PJ. Iron-sulfur cluster disassembly in the FNR protein of *Escherichia coli* by O₂: [4Fe-4S] to [2Fe-2S] conversion with loss of biological activity. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 1997; 94:6087-92.
9. Volbeda A, Darnault C, Renoux O, Nicolet Y, Fontecilla-Camps JC. The crystal structure of the global anaerobic transcriptional regulator FNR explains its extremely fine-tuned monomer-dimer equilibrium. *Science Advances* 2015; 1:e1501086.